

THE COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF “ARROWSMITH” AND “CITADEL” .

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Abstract: This article compares the medical issues of ‘Citadel’ the work of A. J. Cronin and by Sinclair Lewis’s “Arrowsmith” .

Key words: mining, medical ethics, Andrew Manson, “*The Citadel*” medical student, ethical. Arrowsmith.

The Citadel relates the story of Andrew Manson, a romantic young Scottish doctor, modeled closely on Cronin himself.

The story of her struggles to make him realize his mistakes. This is a book about medical ethics and what it means to be a doctor. It is a great read and all.

The Citadel is the morality tale of the initially idealistic Scottish Doctor Andrew Manson who starts off working in the mining towns of the South Wales valleys where he makes liberal use of explosives to remedy public health nuisances before descending into the vanity fair of fashionable London doctors, who specialize.

The Citadel follows the life of Andrew Manson, a young and idealistic Scottish doctor, as he navigates the challenges of practicing medicine across interwar Wales and England. [S. O’Mahoney, ‘A. J. Cronin and The Citadel: did a work of fiction contribute to the foundation of the NHS?’, in *J. Roy Coll Physicians Edinb* 2012, 42: 172–8]

Martin Arrowsmith, the novel's protagonist, is born and raised in the small Midwestern town of Elk Mills where he develops an interest in science and spends his free hours reading through *Gray's Anatomy* and other books in the office of the town's doctor, Doc Vickerson. This early education is supplemented when he goes off to college and eventually becomes a medical student at the University of Winamac, where he meets his life-time mentor, Max Gottlieb, a German professor

committed to laboratory science and research.

While in medical school, Martin dates a girl named Madeleine Fox, a snobbish, educated doctoral student of literature and becomes engaged to her, only to leave

her later for Leora Tozer, a down-to-earth nurse in training, whom he will love and live with until the end of her life. [K. C. Calman, *Medical Education: Past Present and Future*. OUP, 2007]

Also, while at Winnemac, under the wing of Gottlieb, Martin develops a deep-rooted love for the laboratory and lashes out against "commercialism" and the faults of the practicing physician versus the ideals of true science and research. Nevertheless, Martin, after graduating from Winamac, must abandon his "true science" because he has married Leora and now has a wife to support. Martin and Leora move to Leora's hometown of Wheat Sylvania where Martin becomes a country doctor about whom the townspeople gossip. Although he is at times successful, he never gains the trust of the community as a whole and loses a patient, in his early days. Leora also has a miscarriage during their time in Wheat Sylvania. Feeling as though he has failed in Wheat Sylvania, Martina and Leora move to Nautilus, a city in the Midwest. [S. O'Mahoney, 'A. J. Cronin and *The Citadel*: did a work of fiction contribute to the foundation of the NHS?', in *J. Roy Coll Physicians Edinb* 2012, 42: 172–8]

The Citadel enormously and re-read it perhaps ten years ago, and at that time marked up almost thirty passages of interest. On the present occasion the re-reading was more holistic and I was searching for broader messages in the text.

The Citadel has a particular emphasis on two areas. First, the work of the doctor in a poor community and how his work is transformed as the doctor moves to London and private practice. Second is the impact that the novel had on the delivery of health services in the United Kingdom. This is particularly important in terms of the content, geographical location and timing of the book and its translation into a film. This article will first briefly discuss the author, A. J. Cronin, then the basis of the novel, its wider impact and finally the more general issue of

literature and medicine. [["A. J. Cronin, author of 'Citadel' and 'Keys of the Kingdom', dies"](#). *New York Times*. 10 January 1981. Retrieved 22 May 2021.

Archibald Joseph Cronin was born in Cardross, Dunbartonshire, in 1896. He subsequently moved to Glasgow and was destined either for the Church or medicine, and he chose medicine. He entered the University of Glasgow in 1914 with a Carnegie Scholarship and between 1916–17 he was abroad for naval service. He graduated in 1919 with honors. He gained a number of additional qualifications including a DPH, an MRCP and an MD on "The History of Aneurysm". (This topic features in *The Citadel* when the main character, Dr

Manson, is asked a question in his medical postgraduate examination on aneurysms, and gives the distinguished examiner a very learned reply.) Cronin trained in various hospitals in the West of Scotland, Dublin and in Tredegar, a mining town in South Wales. He was appointed as a Medical Inspector of Mines and reported on coal-dust inhalation and lung disease. He subsequently moved to

London and private practice. [A. J. Cronin, [*Adventures in Two Worlds*](#). Boston: Little, Brown and Company, 1952, pp. 261–262]

In 1930 he was forced to take six months' rest because of a duodenal ulcer and it was then that he wrote his first novel, *Hatter's Castle*. It was an immediate success. He subsequently published *The Stars Look Down*, *The Keys of the Kingdom*, *The Green Years* and many more. *The Citadel* was published in 1937, with a film version produced in 1938; as will be noted, he used much of his professional career as a background to the book. Cronin died in 1981.

The Citadel begins as Dr Andrew Manson, a newly qualified doctor and a graduate of St Andrews/Dundee, arrives in a small Welsh mining village to take up his first clinical post as assistant to a general practitioner. The clinical cases are very real, from his first case of typhoid through to a broken arm in a pit collapse requiring an on-the-spot amputation in very cramped conditions. The men, as miners, have a company insurance policy and they can change doctors as they wish, which is fortunate: Dr Manson is often critical of the quality of the work of the other doctors in the town.[A. J. Cronin, [*Adventures in Two Worlds*](#). Boston: Little, Brown and Company, 1952, pp. 261–262.]

Her unstinting support enables Manson to travel to London, successfully defend his research paper, and qualify for the advanced degree—an amazing set of accomplishments for a graduate of an undistinguished medical school, practicing in a small town. In *The Citadel*, Cronin preaches many lessons: hard work, conscientious patient care, and intellectual curiosity are the keys to success in medicine; knowledge and integrity count for much more in life than money; doctors need continuing education to remain current and to serve their patients well. In each of Manson's professional endeavors, he befriends a colorful colleague whose lack of material success belies a keen intellect and great personal integrity. These "diamonds in the rough" reemerge later in Manson's life to help him through professional and personal difficulties. Again in his second position, Manson clashes with the powers that be. He resigns his provincial post and takes Christine off to London, where he hopes to become a specialist in lung disease and become an attending physician at a respected

London hospital. He I Seth Kivnick, MD, is a surgeon at the SCPMG West Los Angeles Medical Center. [A. J. Cronin and J. A. Fisher, "A. J. Cronin--physician, author, Boston: Twayne Publishers, 1985]

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